

AWARENESS-RAISING STRATEGIES FOR LEARNERS' DIVERGENCE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6047122>

Iroda Murodova

Samarkand State University, Kattakurgan branch

Annotation: *This article discusses strategies to increase student divergence awareness.*

Introduction

Sometimes communication with non-native speaker of the language can reveal the mismatch between his/her pragmatic behavior and expected patterns in the language. This phenomenon is called as divergence and assumed to stem from various reasons despite of advanced level knowledge of the speaker in the language (two of which will be explored below). Therefore, Ishihara (2011) notes that “indeed, pragmatic ability is one of the most complex and challenging aspects of communicative competence”. However, according to Cohen and Olshtain (1993) learners may enhance their pragmatic abilities without any precise instruction provided in the classroom, still; it may take averagely 10 years to pragmatically succeed in the language. In the textbook called “Teaching and Learning Pragmatics” by Noriko Ishihara and Andrew D. Cohen five common causes of learners’ divergence from pragmatic norms are supplied and I wanted to elaborate on two of them which have affected my students most. They are: **1) negative transfer of pragmatic norms; 2) limited L2 grammatical ability.**

1. Negative transfer of pragmatic norms

Mukhalad Almutalabi (2015) defines that “negative pragmatic transfer is a crucial phenomenon that directly influences the performance of language being a linguistic strategy that is used by non-native speakers while trying to communicate in the target language due to certain pragmatic assumptions”. While Ishihara further explains about the negative pragmatic transfer that:

When learners do not know pragmatic norms in the target language or when they assume that their own pragmatic norms apply in the given situation in the target culture, they may consciously or unconsciously depend on the norms that apply for that situation when using their first, dominant, or some other language.

(Ishihara-Cohen, 2010, p.78)

The transfer can be a positive when learner' pragmatic norms in L1 are similar to L2, but if norms are different this may result in negative consequences like awkwardness, misunderstanding and even a breakdown of communication. The reason behind my choice of this category of divergence is its common occurrence in our classrooms due to the difference between indirect Asian culture and relatively direct culture of English language. For example Korean boy or girl who is learning Japanese language gives presentations and when he/she is complimented by other group mates, he/she may reflect saying "not, that is not true" which is accepted as a modesty because of similarity of the pragmatic norms in two languages, but when Korean learner says so to the his American friends, it would cause offense or direct rejection of their opinion due to difference between pragmatic norms. According to the one of my adult learners' report, she visited Germany because of periodical exchange program and stayed at host home. Even though she was too hungry she said "No, I am not hungry" to the food offer of the host and deprived of food that day because of her pragmatic norms of politeness in Uzbek language. Because the host was from direct culture who perceived the response as it is.

2. Limited L2 grammatical ability

Learner's advanced knowledge in grammar does not necessarily refer to his/her pragmatic competence. Those who excel in grammar and produce accurate grammatical language may not be competent to succeed pragmatically (Ishihara & Cohen, 2010). However "learners who demonstrate very little grammatical accuracy may still be able to interpret messages as intended and produce pragmatically appropriate utterances" according to Schmidt (1983). The reason why grammatical ability and pragmatic competence are integral is that students can better comprehend the delivered message when they are aware of these structures included in the message. For example, students relatively limited in grammar say just "thanks" in order to represent gratitude, which is not pragmatically appropriate for every or any situation. Therefore, taking into consideration of their social and cultural needs is a must. Students should be aware of the existing norms in their own society to identify the differences and similarities of pragmatic norms between L1 and L2 in order to prevent the occurrence of pragmatic failure in target language. To implement this "language teachers can support learners when they attempt to produce pragmatically appropriate language and interpret meaning as intended by others in the L2 community" (Ishihara & Cohen, 2010).

Three awareness-raising tasks for teaching pragmatics that you can use with your learners to address these divergences.

Activity1. The students are provided with special structures and phrases before asking them to do this exercise as an input.

Party Time

ESL Making Request and Suggestions Activity - Writing, Listening and Speaking - Pre-intermediate (A2) - 30 minutes

In this requests and suggestions activity, students plan and organize a class party by making, accepting and refusing requests and suggestions. The students are divided into pairs and each pair is given a copy of the worksheet. The students are told that they are going to organize a class party and that there is an unlimited budget as the teacher is going to pay for everything! The pairs then make, accept and refuse suggestions and write their agreed-on ideas for the party in a table on the worksheet. When the students have finished, each pair joins with another pair to make a group of four. The students then discuss their suggestions for the party and write the best ideas in a second table. When the students have completed their plans, they take it in turns to make requests to each other to organize and complete tasks in preparation for the party, e.g. 'Could you go to the shop and buy ten bottles of Champagne?' Students only agree to a request if they genuinely think they wouldn't mind doing it. When a student agrees to a request, their name and accepted task is written in the table. If students don't want to do something, they decline the request and explain why. When everyone has finished, groups tell the class about their party plans and what each student is going to do in preparation for the party. Afterwards, the class votes for the group with the best party ideas.

MAKING REQUESTS
Party Time

A. You are going to organize a class party. There is an unlimited budget as the teacher is going to pay for everything! In pairs, make, accept and refuse suggestions and write your agreed-on ideas for the party in the table below.
 Useful language for making suggestions: Let's... We could... Why don't we...? How about...?

Where to have the party	
When to have the party	
Music and Entertainment e.g. a band, a DJ, games, etc.	
Food for the party	
Drinks for the party	
Things to make, buy and get, e.g. decorations, cutlery, chairs, etc.	
Things to do beforehand, e.g. make a flyer, invitations, etc.	
Other ideas	

B. Now, join with another pair to make a group of four. Discuss your suggestions for the party and write the best ideas below. Then, take it in turns to make requests to each other to organize and complete tasks in preparation for the party. When a student agrees to a request, write their accepted task and name in the table.
 Useful language for making requests: Can you...? Could you...? Would you mind...ing...?

	Best ideas	Task	Student's name
Where			
When			
Music & Entertainment			
Food			
Drinks			
Things to make, buy and get			
Things to do beforehand			
Other ideas			

Teach-This.com © 2017 Permission granted to reproduce for classroom use.

Activity2. At the end of the activity students are encouraged to go through pragmatics considering why they are using these special terms to complain and when to use which complaint pattern and how to properly answer for each complaint depending of formality, politeness and social distance. This activity is aimed to addressing the negative pragmatic transform divergence since activity

requires students to apologize to the complaints appropriately depending on the different situations.

Dealing with Complaints

ESL Complaints Role-Play - Listening and Speaking Activity - Intermediate (B1) - 30 minutes

In this making and dealing with complaints role-play activity, students practice making and dealing with complaints. The students begin by brainstorming ten situations in which people make complaints. Write and number the students' ideas on the board. Next, give each pair of students a set of cards, which they shuffle and place face down on the table. The students then role-play complaints for the situations on the board. The aim is to use the expressions on the cards as part of their role-play. In each role-play, students take it in turns to be the person complaining and the person dealing with the complaint. The students start with the first scenario on the board and spend a short time thinking about what they are going to say. Each student then takes one card from the top of the pile. The students begin the role-play and as quickly as they can, they use the expression on the card in a complete sentence. When they have done this, and while continuing the role-play, they take another card and repeat the process. The aim is to use as many of the expressions as they can during the role-play. Students score one point for each correctly used expression. The students then shuffle the cards, swap roles, and move on to the second role-play situation. The student with the most points at the end of the activity wins.

COMPLAINING AND APOLOGIZING
Dealing with Complaints

I'm sorry to trouble you, but...	I'm sorry to hear that...	Unfortunately, this was unavoidable as...
Is there anything else...?	Leave it with me and...	Oh dear, I'm...
I've got a bit of a problem, you see...	Would it help if...?	Not to worry, I'll...
OK, what I'll do is...	Let me straighten this out and I will...	Is there any chance...?
Would you mind...?	No problem, I'll...	This was because...
I'll look into...	Please tell me exactly what...	I suggest you leave it with us and we'll...

Teach-This.com © 2017. Permission granted to reproduce for classroom use.

Activity3. This activity is also targeted to raise their awareness about negative transform of pragmatic norms as they are discussing the concept of etiquette and practicing to give advice to various people and respond this advice properly.

Advice for the Modern World

ESL Giving Advice Game - Reading, Writing, Listening and Speaking Activity - Pre-intermediate (A2) - 40 minutes

In this giving advice situations activity, students play a game where they give advice for modern-day situations. This activity helps to teach students how to give advice using four different structures. After practicing the four structures for giving advice and discussing the concept of etiquette, divide the students into pairs. Working together, the students write four pieces of advice for the modern-day situations on the worksheet using a different structure for giving advice each time. The situations cover things like using a mobile phone, using social networks, etc. When the students have finished, each pair joins with another pair. One pair chooses a modern-day situation at random and reads one of their pieces of advice to the other pair. The other pair then guesses which situation the advice is for. If the pair guesses correctly, they score four points. If they guess incorrectly, the pair reads a second piece of advice for three points and so on. When a pair guesses a situation successfully or all four pieces of advice have been read out, the pairs swap roles. This process continues until both pairs have given advice for all the situations on their worksheet. The pairs then play a second round where they take it in turns to read out all four pieces of advice for each modern-day situation. If a pair has a piece of advice that is different from the other pair, they score a point. The pair with the most points at the end of the game wins.

TEACHTHIS HELPING YOU REACH YOUR POTENTIAL GIVING FOR AND GIVING ADVICE
Advice for the Modern World

A. Complete the four sentences with advice for people visiting your country for the first time.

1. You should (n't)
2. You'd better (not)
3. If I were you,
4. You ought (not) to

B. Now, work with a partner. Write four pieces of advice for the modern-day situations below. Use a different structure for giving advice each time.

Using mobile phones	1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____ 4. _____
Using social networking sites	1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____ 4. _____
Meeting People	1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____ 4. _____
Getting around	1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____ 4. _____
Visiting someone's home	1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____ 4. _____
Dining out	1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____ 4. _____

C. Join with another pair. Take it in turns to choose a situation at random and read one of your pieces of advice to the other pair. The other pair has to guess which situation the advice is for. If the pair guesses correctly, they score four points. If they guess incorrectly, read a second piece of advice. The pair then guesses again for three points and so on.

Teach-This.com © 2017. Permission granted to reproduce for classroom use.

REFERENCES:

1. Noriko Ishihara and Andrew D. Cohen.(2010).Teaching and Learning Pragmatics.ISBN: 978-1-4082-0457-3.
2. <https://www.teach-this.com/>

